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Electrical Behavior of Green-Synthesized Nano Silver Particles Embedded in Polyurethane: Numerical and Experimental Studies

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the electrical properties of a nanocomposite composed of green-synthesized silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) embedded in a polyurethane (PU) matrix, employing both experimental and numerical methods. The AgNPs were synthesized using an eco-friendly approach, utilizing non-toxic phytochemicals derived from *Urtica dioica* (stinging nettle) as reducing and stabilizing agents. These nanoparticles were then integrated into PU matrices, and their dispersion, structural integrity, and electrical characteristics were thoroughly analyzed. To predict the composite's electrical behavior, finite element method (FEM) simulations were performed using Digimat software, based on a representative volume element (RVE) model. The results revealed that electrical conductivity increases with higher concentrations of AgNPs and applied pressure, reaching a maximum conductivity of 1.4S/m at 43.3 wt.% AgNPs filler under 20 kPa pressure. Additionally, the study demonstrated that introducing a washing step prior to combining AgNPs with PU reduces the concentration of phyto-stabilizers, enhancing nanoparticle dispersion, composite quality, and overall electrical conductivity. This research highlights the potential of green-synthesized nanocomposites for advanced electrical applications.

1 | Introduction

There is a growing interest in developing environmentally benign methods to synthesize nanoparticles to minimize their adverse effect on the environment and human health. Several methods are available to synthesize nanoparticles, including chemical, physical, photochemical, and green synthesis [1–5]. Among the chemical methods, Turkevich [6], Lee-Meisel [7], and polyol [8] processes are examples of chemical reduction techniques. These

techniques are often straightforward, allowing for easy control of size and shape and yielding large quantities of nanoparticles [4, 9]. However, these methods use hazardous reactants. Since nanoparticles tend to aggregate, they require stabilizing agents that may leave chemical residuals on the nanoparticle surface and cause environmental problems because of their toxicity [9]. Therefore, more research, development, and innovation in nanotechnology are required to develop more sustainable approaches.

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Summary

- AgNPs synthesized using *Urtica dioica* as a reducing and stabilizing agent
- The stabilizer in AgNPs affects nanocomposite dispersion and conductivity.
- Electrical conductivity increases with the concentration of AgNPs in PU.
- The maximum composite conductivity achieved is 1.4 S/m for 43.3 wt.% AgNPs.
- FE-RVE simulation examines stabilizer impact on electrical conductivity.

Technological procedures that use living cells or biomass in a modified state to form nanoparticles are called bionanotechnology. This so-called “green synthesis” involves using plant tissues such as leaves, roots, peels, seeds, and so forth; and microorganisms such as bacteria, yeast, fungi, and so forth [10]. The plant tissues have biomolecules (phytochemicals), including enzymes, proteins, amino acids, vitamins, polysaccharides, and organic acids, which may function as reducing agents, capping agents, or simultaneously as both [11]. The concentration of metal precursor and plant extract significantly influences the nanoparticles' morphology and size [1, 12]. Among various metal nanoparticles synthesized by green methods, silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are particularly interesting due to their unique antimicrobial, optical, electrical, and thermal properties [13]. These properties make AgNPs suitable for biosensors, polymer composites, superconducting materials, cosmetic products, electronic components, catalysis, photonics, sensing and monitoring, and antimicrobial applications. AgNPs are advantageous for usage in electronics-related applications such as conductive inks, sensors, flexible electronics, and smart fabrics [1, 4, 9, 14, 15].

Integrating metal nanoparticles like AgNPs into polymers using solution mixing, melt mixing, and in situ polymerization methods produces electrically conductive polymer composites (ECPCs). The ECPCs merge the benefits of the polymer matrix—such as low density, easy processing, and good flexibility—with the properties of metal nanoparticles [16]. ECPCs that incorporate elastomers with high elongation and excellent flexibility, such as thermoplastic polyurethane (PU), are in high demand for applications like strain sensors, electromagnetic interference (EMI) shields, and tissue engineering [17]. To sum up, integrating AgNPs into PU results in ECPCs, which are conductive, lightweight, and adaptable to various shapes and forms [17]. However, multiple factors affect the electrical performance of composites, including the volume/mass fraction of silver within the composite, the shape and size of filler/s, the dispersion of nanoparticles, the presence of an oxide layer, the composite fabrication technique, and the nature of matrix [17, 18].

Significant research was carried out using green AgNPs as conductive fillers in ECPCs. Taesuwan et al. [19] successfully synthesized green AgNPs using sugarcane leaves and integrated these nanoparticles into a hydrogel-based polyvinyl matrix. The

highest conductivity was 0.22 S/m for a 50 mM silver nitrate solution. Cheng et al. [20] utilized glucose as a reducing agent to synthesize silver AgNPs with a size distribution ranging from 80 to 100 nm. Compared to traditional hydrazine hydrate methods, the green-prepared AgNPs showed better uniform size, dispersion, stability, and no residual solvents. These nanoparticles were incorporated into hyperbranched polyurethane acrylate as a filler to produce ink with a conductive 2.3×10^5 S/m for 80 wt.% of the filler. In a unique green method, Dinh et al. [21] explored the production of AgNPs in graphene oxide by in situ ultrasonication using vitamin C as a reducing agent of AgNO_3 . An AgNPs/rGO film was obtained by spin coating a solution of AgNPs/GO onto a glass substrate and then reducing it on H_2 flow at 500°C. It was noted that reducing the duration of ultrasonication resulted in a decrease in AgNP size and a drop in resistivity. The film exhibited a low resistance value of $270 \Omega \text{ cm}^{-1}$ after just 1 min of ultrasonication because the smaller AgNP size creates better conductive networks. Aigbodion [21] utilized cashew leaves that contain anacardic acid to reduce Ag^+ to AgNPs. Then, 0.5 wt.% of AgNPs was added to various concentrations of carbon nanotubes and mixed with epoxy, forming several composite materials. It was found that the introduction of 0.5 wt.% carbon nanotubes (CNT) decorated with 0.5 wt.% AgNPs led to a notable enhancement in the electrical conductivity of the epoxy polymer, from 5.6×10^{-13} to 9.1×10^{-3} S/cm. Naysmith et al. [22] synthesized AgNPs employing fresh lime peels as a reducing agent and utilized a statistical approach of the Plackett–Burman method to limit the issues related to the polydispersity and repeatability of the biotechnology method. These authors found that AgNO_3 concentration and reaction temperature were statistically significant in the AgNP morphology. Green AgNPs were combined with the conjugated polymer polypyrrole (Ppy) via in situ polymerization. The resultant coated particles exhibited outstanding electrical characteristics, featuring a low electrical resistance of 37 Ω , rendering them well-suited for applications in smart textiles [23]. These composites leverage the unique properties of AgNPs, which can be synthesized using green methods to reduce the environmental impact [19, 23]. However, none of these studies have explored the impact of stabilizers on the performance of green AgNPs when used as a filler in metal-polymer composites.

Nanoparticles enhance electrical conductivity due to their high surface area and silver's excellent conductivity, improving electron transfer. The conductivity mechanism of ECPCs consists of two types: tunneling effect and Ohmic conductance [24]. The tunneling effect occurs with lower filler concentration, where fillers are encased in a polymer layer that forms a barrier exceeding the free electron energy, but there is still some probability for the electrons to hop the barrier. As filler loading reaches the percolation threshold, conductive networks are formed within the polymer matrix, creating low-resistance paths for free electron movement. Consequently, Ohmic conductance becomes the predominant mechanism. As described by percolation theory, the change from tunneling effect to Ohmic conductance with increased filler content reflects a sudden change in ECPCs' conductivity [13].

The electrical behavior of conductive composites has been studied by developing numerous numerical and theoretical models, including molecular dynamics, Brownian dynamics,

and Finite Element (FE) analysis. Among them, the representative volume element (RVE) model, often combined with FE methods, is particularly effective in estimating material properties [24–26]. Studies have shown the RVE-FE model's accuracy in predicting the electrical conductivity of composites, such as epoxy composites with multi-walled carbon nanotubes [27, 28]. In our previous research, we have also demonstrated its ability to simulate percolation thresholds and pressure-induced percolation transitions (PIPT) in micro-silver and micro-copper composites, correlating well with experimental results [29, 30]. However, the RVE-FE model has not yet been applied to examine the impact of impurities on the conductivity of metal-polymer composites. This research aims to fill that gap by using the RVE-FE model to study the influence of stabilizers in green-synthesized AgNPs on the electrical properties of polyurethane composites.

In this study, we describe the laboratory preparation of silver nanoparticles using a biotechnological method. Different concentrations of green AgNPs were added to PU using the solution mixing method. The PU-AgNPs were characterized using an optical microscope and scanning electron microscope (SEM), and a developed set-up with a digital multimeter was used to measure the electrical conductivity. Numerical simulation using the FE-RVE method and DIGIMAT software was employed to describe the conductivity of the composite. Furthermore, this study experimentally assesses the effect of stabilizing phyto-coating on the electrical properties of the AgNPs/PU composite thin film and using FE-RVE.

2 | Experimental

2.1 | AgNPs/PU Nanocomposite Preparations

2.1.1 | Chemicals Used

Thermoplastic polyurethane (PU) pellets were provided by BASF plc, UK, bearing the trademark Elastollan 1180 A 10,000. The Merck Company in the UK provided N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF, anhydrous, >99.8%) and Isopropanol (Fisher, >99.8%). For the preparation of AgNPs, silver nitrate AgNO_3 (Penta Chemicals, Czech Republic) was used as a precursor of Ag ions and fresh leaves of *Urtica dioica* (UR) as a phyto-precursor of reducing and stabilizing compounds. All chemicals were used in their original form.

2.1.2 | Bioreduction of Silver Nanoparticles

Fresh plant (leaves) of *Urtica dioica* (UR), known for phyto-reductive properties, originated from enzymes (hydrogenases, reductases) and phytochemicals such as terpenoids, flavonoids, phenols, and dihydric phenols [31, 32] were thoroughly rinsed with distilled water, dried (80°C) and crushed. Aqueous extract of phytochemicals was prepared by mixing 2.5 g of UR and 500 mL of distilled water heated to 80°C. After 10 min of leaching, the mixture was first quickly filtered through a strainer and then filtered once more through a paper filter. Cooled down to room temperature, the phytochemical precursor was mixed (1:1) with silver nitrate at a concentration

of 100 mmol·dm⁻³ to prepare AgNPs. Nanoparticles were centrifuged the next day (7000 rpm, 10 min) and kept in a dark bottle.

2.1.3 | Removing Stabilizers

The synthesized green AgNPs were covered by a stabilizer that might be a complex mixture of photochemicals attached to the AgNP surface via hydrogen bonding and π - π stacking. However, the specific composition of the stabilizer was not analyzed in this work. Due to the coating on the AgNPs, the nanoparticles were not conductive. Therefore, they were washed before being incorporated into the polymer. Two solvents, Isopropanol and DMF, were separately used to try to remove the stabilizer in the following manner: 50 mL of solvent was introduced to the particles, followed by sonication for 30 min at 25°C. Subsequently, the combined solution underwent separation through centrifugation at 8500 rpm for 10 min. The liquid floating above the particles was poured out of the centrifuge tube. The washing process with DMF or Isopropanol was repeated twice. Only DMF could remove part of the stabilizer, so the particles were conductive. DMF can remove the phytochemical coating without causing aggregation or oxidation of the AgNPs, thereby preserving their colloidal stability. This will be explained in the results and discussion section.

2.1.4 | Polymer Composite Preparation

Initially, a specified quantity of polyurethane pellets was initially weighed out to create a composite material. Subsequently, the polyurethane pellets were introduced into a beaker on top of a hot plate within a fume hood. Following this, DMF solvent was slowly incorporated into the polymer, continuously stirring at 60°C, ensuring complete dissolution. The polymer-to-solvent ratio was fine-tuned to attain a uniform and viscous solution, with a concentration of 15 wt.% polyurethane in DMF. In a typical fabrication process, an appropriate quantity of washed AgNPs synthesized via the green method was measured and introduced into the prepared PU-DMF solution. Since a small amount of DMF remained on the AgNPs during the washing process, the viscosity of the PU/DMF/AgNPs mixture decreased when the AgNPs were added. This lower viscosity made the mixture unsuitable for spin coating. Consequently, the resulting solution was stirred at 300 rpm and heated at 95°C to eliminate excess DMF and increase the mixture's viscosity. A 0.3 mL portion of the solution containing PU/DMF/AgNPs was pipetted onto a Teflon sheet and applied to a spin coater (Ossila) at 1200 rpm for 10 s. The Teflon-coated film with a composite was allowed to dry under the fume hood for 1 day. This process produced a series of film polymer composites of AgNPs/PU with different concentrations of green AgNPs ranging from 7 to 44 wt.%. This range widens from the minimal silver content to the maximum amount that can be incorporated without causing structural damage to the polymer matrix film. This enables a systematic investigation of how variations in silver content influence electrical conductivity. Furthermore, the influence of applied pressure on electrical conductivity for each concentration level has also been explored.

TABLE 1 | The concentration of AgNPs and stabilizer in AgNPs-PU composite films obtained by TGA.

Sample	Mass fraction of AgNPs (wt.%)	Mass fraction of stabilizer (wt.%)	Volume fraction of AgNPs (vol.%)	Volume fraction of stabilizer (vol.%)
1	6.8	1.4	0.82	1.78
2	9.6	1.8	1.19	2.35
3	12.8	2.4	1.64	3.23
4	20.5	7.6	2.81	10.9
5	25.2	7.9	3.63	12.0
6	36.2	11.3	5.89	19.3
7	43.3	12.7	7.71	23.7

2.2 | Nanocomposite Characterization and Modeling

2.2.1 | Optical Microscopy

In this research, an Alicona InfiniteFocus Optical Microscope featuring a magnification of 50× was utilized to examine the dispersion of AgNPs within the composites. The investigation encompassed two scenarios: one involving the use of synthesized nanoparticles without a washing step and the other employing a washing step with DMF as an integral part of the technique.

2.2.2 | Electron Microscopy

The size and morphology of fresh bioreduced AgNPs and NPs distributed in thin PU film were investigated using the scanning transmission electron microscope (STEM) JEOL JSM-7610F Plus, Tokyo, Japan, with a Schottky cathode at 30 keV in a high vacuum chamber. Fresh colloidal solution with AgNPs was dropped on a copper/formvar grid. A piece of a thin self-standing AgNPs-PU film was directly placed into the STEM grids holder. Elemental composition analysis and mapping were performed using the energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscope (EDS) AZtec Ultima Max 65 (Oxford Instruments, Abingdon, UK). JMicroVision software was used to measure the longest line length of 200 colloidal nanoparticles in an electron micrograph to estimate the size distribution of AgNPs.

Another SEM instrument (MIRA 3, Tescan, Czech Republic) was employed to investigate the particle distribution in the composites from two different perspective views, including cross-sectional and in-plane. Originally, film composites were affixed onto the specimen stage and coated with a 5 nm platinum stratum to ensure sample conductivity throughout the stage.

2.3 | Cross-Sectional View

A cold mounting methodology was employed to stabilize the composite films in a perpendicular orientation, facilitating the capture of images across the film's thickness using optical and scanning electron microscopies. Furthermore, these images enable us to precisely measure the thickness of the slender films

derived from the spin-coating process. The cold mounting procedure involved positioning the film in an upright stance at the center of a molding cup, followed by the addition of a mixture comprising bisphenol-A-(epichlorohydrin) epoxy resin and oxirane, mono[(C12-14-alkyloxy)methyl] as the resin component and triethylenetetramine as the hardener. Preceding this, the film was affixed with Sellotape to maintain its upright position on the molding cup. Subsequently, the mixture was allowed to solidify at room temperature for 24 h. The sample was then bisected, cleansed with distilled water, and subjected to grinding and polishing processes. Afterwards, it was thoroughly washed several times with water and isopropanol to prepare it for microscopic analysis.

2.3.1 | Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA)

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed using a TA Q-600 instrument. Approximately 5 mg of each sample was heated from 30°C to 600°C at a rate of 20°C/min under a constant nitrogen flow of 20 mL/min. The silver and stabilizer contents in AgNPs-PU films were quantified through TGA, as shown in Table 1. The volume fractions were calculated using the density of silver (10.49 g cm⁻³) and PU (1.110 g cm⁻³) and assumed that the density of stabilizers was 1 g cm⁻³.

2.3.2 | Electrical Conductivity Measurement

The electrical conductivity of the composites through the thickness (z-axis) was evaluated at various pressures using a multi-meter set-up, as reported in the previous publication [29, 30]. A brief description is presented herein. The upper and lower surfaces of the AgNPs-PU film were pasted with copper foils measuring 1 × 1 cm² each. Then, copper foils were attached to the electrodes, ensuring a reliable electrical connection between the electrodes and the composite film. Subsequently, a cuboid of insulating material of the same dimensions was positioned on top of the copper foils. Several calibrated masses were applied to the system to compress the composite film, corresponding to 0.5, 1, 2, 5, 10, 15, and 20 kPa pressure. Finally, the electrical resistance of the compressed film was measured through the thickness, utilizing a digital multimeter (UNI-T, UT58A). Each measurement underwent three repetitions, and the average values are reported. The in-plane conductivity of the AgNPs-PU films was

also tested by placing the probes 1 mm apart, but the resistance values exceeded 200 M Ω , which is the upper measurement limit of the multimeter, indicating that the composites might be non-conductive in the plane direction.

2.3.3 | Digimat FE Modeling

In this investigation, the simulation of nanocomposite electrical conductivity was conducted utilizing the finite element method centered on the representative volume element (FE-RVE) model using MSC Software Digimat-FE (e-Xstream engineering, 2021.3 version, Belgium). Generally, the simulation deploys the constituent form of Ohm's law to calculate the electrical conductivity of the AgNPs-PU films. In our model, the conduction is assumed to be predominantly ohmic. The electrical conductivity of pure silver is 6.30×10^7 S/m. Polyurethane is modeled with a very low conductivity of 10^{-14} S/m, while the stabilizer is assigned a conductivity of 10^{-8} S/m. Quantum effects, like tunneling or hopping, are indirectly reflected in the network's percolation behavior. The software can create RVEs based on the input data and assumptions. The simulation incorporated stabilizers because optical microscopy and conductivity measurements revealed that stabilizer levels directly influence the electrical performance of AgNPs-PU composites. TGA also determined the amount of these stabilizers in the composite. To investigate the efficiency of the FE-RVE model, the following assumptions were adopted and executed through simulation: (a) silver nanoparticles and stabilizer are spherical particles, (b) the size of the silver nanoparticles was 15 nm, and the stabilizers consisted of 2 nm size particles; (c) both particles can contact each other, penetrate, and form an agglomeration site; (d) both particles were randomly distributed throughout the composites; (e) the size of the RVEs was the same for all the composites ($0.4 \times 0.4 \times 0.4 \mu\text{m}^3$); (f) number of meshes for all the composites was 216,000 ($60 \times 60 \times 60$) based on a basic mesh convergence study; (g) the results presented are the average outcomes derived from conducting the simulations a minimum of three times; (h) density of silver was 10.49 g cm^{-3} , and the density of stabilizer was assumed to be 1 g cm^{-3} , representative of organic compounds.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | Green Silver Nanoparticle Synthesis and Characterization

Silver nanoparticles were prepared by a biotechnological route using a simple aqueous leachate from UR and a silver nitrate precursor with a $100 \text{ mmol} \cdot \text{dm}^{-3}$ concentration. Nanoparticles are relatively small, with a wider size distribution from 10 to 30 nm and an average size value of 17 nm (see Figure 1). The occurrence of nanoparticles (seeds) below 10 nm was also observed from the electron images. The shape of the particles is irregular; from higher magnifications, it can be concluded that they have a polygonal morphology.

From the illustrative electron images in Figure 2, it can be seen that the dispersion of nanocrystalline silver in PU is uniform, which is confirmed by energy dispersive x-ray mapping of

silver in the matrix (Figure 2b). A small amount of chloride ions (transformed into AgCl) probably originates from the used plant biomass, and chloride anions are often detected in EDS spectra during photosynthesis.

Figure 3 presents the TGA results of the green synthesized AgNPs. The graph indicates a mass reduction from 100% to 62% from 40°C to 750°C. Approximately 38% of the mass decomposes at high temperatures, which is attributed to the presence of phyto-stabilizing compounds. Two peaks are observed in the graph. The first peak, ranging from 100°C to 350°C, corresponds to approximately 16% mass loss and may indicate light organic compounds. The second peak, occurring between 550°C and 700°C, represents about 23% of the mass loss and may correspond to heavy organic compounds and carbon. It needs to be noted that these stabilizing agents play a crucial role in preventing particle agglomeration by ensuring the dispersion of individual nano-silver particles [33, 34].

3.2 | Polymer Nanocomposite AgNPs-PU

Initially, we prepared composite AgNPs-PU samples without the DMF washing step. It was found that they were neither conductive in-plane nor through the thickness, even under a pressure of 20 kPa. Figure 4a shows the optical microscopy image of the AgNPs-PU composite without the washing step. As can be seen from Figure 4a, the stabilizers (shown in black) encapsulate the agglomerated silver nanoparticles, blocking the interaction between adjacent AgNP agglomerates. This prevented the formation of electron pathways between agglomerated AgNP groups. The stabilizer thickness also increased the spacing between these agglomerates, thus hindering electron mobility through tunneling phenomena. Although the agglomerated AgNPs might be conductive internally in the cluster, the final nanocomposite materials were non-conductive. Additionally, the stabilizer covering the silver particles shows lower particle uniformity and has the potential to impact the dynamic interaction between the filler and the polymer matrix. The uneven dispersion of clusters could be due to the repulsive interactions between the stabilizers and the PU. Figure 5a shows that the composite has lower film quality, presenting gaps within the composite structure and likely affecting the mechanical properties of the films [35].

Since the AgNPs-PU wasn't conductive due to the stabilizer covering the particles, it was decided to wash the AgNPs to remove the stabilizer before incorporating the AgNPs into the polymer. Two solvents were used: Isopropanol or DMF. However, only DMF could remove the stabilizer that is formed by phytochemicals or secondary products after bioreduction. In the Supporting Information, the washing results are shown. Once the washing step of the AgNPs was introduced into the procedure, as it was described in the previous section, AgNPs-PU samples showed that a major part of the stabilizer was removed, as is presented in Figure 4b. It can also be seen that the DMF washing procedure not only removed the stabilizer but also contributed to the even dispersion of the AgNPs, likely due to the 30 min of sonication introduced in the washing procedure. Figure 5b–g shows images corresponding to several concentrations of purified AgNPs integrated into the PU. Images b through g illustrate the uniformity

FIGURE 1 | Electron image of silver nanoparticles prepared by *Urtica* plant (a, b) (scale 100 nm) with size distribution histogram (c) (X—longest line length in nm). Stabilizing components originating from the plant precursor are visible in the bright field (BF) image (b) from the scanning transmission electron microscope as a less contrasting light gray envelope surrounding the nanoparticles.

of AgNPs in the composite, demonstrating a high-quality film without any noticeable defects or gaps.

Figure 6 presents optical microscope images of the composites corresponding to their counterparts in Figure 5. Figure 6b–g show composites prepared using the DMF washing step. It can be seen that the stabilizer concentration was low. The distribution of AgNPs throughout the composites was quite homogeneous. At higher concentrations, AgNPs can aggregate, making them visible under the optical microscope. In contrast, at lower concentrations (as shown in Figure 6g), the nanoparticles are not detectable. The SEM images can provide a clearer representation of the composite. Figure 7 presents SEM images of PU-AgNPs both (a and c) without and (b and d) with stabilizer removal, viewed in-plane and cross-sectionally. The presence of stabilizers increased the occurrence of agglomerated sites, thereby reducing the uniformity of AgNPs across the composite. As shown in Figure 7b, the particles were dispersed more uniformly when the stabilizer was partially removed, thus enhancing the likelihood of neighboring particles connecting to each other. Additionally, the cross-sectional images reveal a blurry cloud around the particles (Figure 7c) associated with stabilizers. The elimination of stabilizer thus resulted in clearer visibility of the particles (Figure 7d). Therefore, only the particles that were washed with DMF created an electrically conductive composite. From this point forward, the paper will only

discuss the PU-AgNPs composites where most of the stabilizer has been removed by DMF washing, and the composite was conductive.

Thermogravimetric analysis was employed to assess the amount of AgNPs and stabilizer incorporated into the PU matrix and the thermal stability of the AgNPs-PU composite. Figure 8 presents the mass loss and its derivative as a function of temperature for the four composites studied. The TGA for the other samples is reported in the Supporting Information. The TGA results revealed significant mass losses primarily due to the decomposition of the stabilizer and PU. Two distinct weight loss stages were observed from the first derivative curve (Figure 8b) within the temperature ranges from 140°C to 290°C and 290°C to 490°C. The initial mass reduction between 140°C and 290°C might correspond to the loss of stabilizer molecules physisorbed onto AgNPs, as this loss increased with increasing concentration of AgNPs in the composite. These weight loss ranges are in agreement with TGA for green AgNPs Figure 3. These accounted for 1.4 to 12 wt.% of the total mass loss, as shown in Table 1. The most substantial mass loss, occurring between approximately 290°C and 490°C, was attributed to the degradation of the PU, which is consistent with the degradation temperatures reported in the literature for similar PU films [36]. Additionally, it was noted that the intensity of the peaks decreased as the PU concentration decreased in the nanocomposite. For all the nanocomposites studied, a residual

FIGURE 2 | Electron images of silver nanoparticles distributed in PU matrix with EDS Ag map (a); (b) EDS spectra showing elemental composition: Ag 7.3 wt%, Cl 1.2 wt%, O 12.4 wt%, and C 79.1 wt%.

FIGURE 3 | Thermal gravimetric analysis is in blue, and the first derivative of TGA curves is in orange for green AgNPs.

mass was observed after approximately 490°C, corresponding to the Ag content in the composite. After 490°C, no weight loss was observed for the AgNPs-PU composite, as has been seen in Figure 3 for green AgNPs. This may indicate that heavy organic compounds from the stabilizer were removed during the washing with DMF. These findings indicate that the nanocomposite remains stable up to around 140°C, making it suitable for its use in medical applications, such as strain sensors. Table 1 provides the concentrations of these samples, presented as both mass

fraction and volume fraction, based on TGA results and the calculations reported by Park et al. [37].

3.3 | Electrical Conductivity Measurements and Simulations

The electrically conductive properties of AgNPs-PU composite for four concentrations of AgNPs are presented in Figure 9. It can be seen that at each pressure, the conductivity of the composite increases with the concentration of silver. The composite exhibits an almost S-shape variation in conductivity with increasing applied pressure. The data indicate that for all composites with varying concentrations of AgNPs, the conductivity changes as the pressure increases. For instance, at AgNPs-PU concentrations of 6.8 and 20.5 wt.%, there is no significant increase in conductivity up to an applied pressure of 10 kPa. However, beyond 10 kPa, there is a dramatic increase in conductivity by five orders of magnitude, even though the composites initially behave like insulators. In contrast, for medium concentrations such as 36.2 wt.% of AgNPs, changes in conductivity occur at a lower applied pressure of 5 kPa, with maximum conductivity reaching 1.28×10^{-3} S/m at the highest compression of 20 kPa. For the highest concentration (43.3 wt.%), a significant increase in conductivity is observed at 2 kPa of compression, transitioning from

FIGURE 4 | Optical microscope images (a) AgNPs-PU nanocomposite without removal of stabilizer and (b) AgNPs-PU nanocomposite when most of the stabilizer is removed. The stabilizer is shown in black, and Ag is shown in gold.

FIGURE 5 | (a) Photo showing the AgNPs-PU composite without the washing step with DMF and (b–g) AgNPs-PU composite with the washing step with DMF for different concentrations of AgNPs: (b) 43.3 wt.%; (c) 25.2 wt.%; (d) 20.6 wt.%; (e) 12.8 wt.%; (f) 9.6 wt.%; (g) 6.8 wt.%.

an insulating state to a highly conductive state with 0.09 S/m at 5 kPa compression—an increase of seven orders of magnitude. Further increasing the pressure from 5 to 20 kPa results in a conductivity increase to 1.4 S/m, representing the maximum conductivity for these composites. In Figure 9, the percolation threshold (PT) concentration can be inferred from the conductivity data at 5, 10, and 20 kPa. For the AgNPs-PU film, the PT can be found at approximately 36.2 wt.% (5.89 vol.%). No change in PT was observed with applied pressure under the studied conditions. A wider concentration range might help better define the PT at each pressure. These results are consistent with those reported by Taesuwan et al. who studied green silver nanoparticles in hydrogels [19], and by Chen et al. who investigated green-synthesized nano-silver incorporated on polyurethane acrylate ink [20]. Similarly, using commercially available AgNPs with particle sizes ranging from 50 to 75 nm, Chen et al. [38] fabricated AgNP/TPU composites with varying AgNP contents (1% to 7% by volume) through melt mixing. They investigated the electrical behavior as a function of temperature and found that their composite exhibited a minimum resistance of $10^4 \Omega \text{ cm}$ (conductivity of 0.01 S/m) at 7 vol.% filler content at temperatures lower than 50°C. The electrical percolation threshold was observed at

4.5% to 5.5% AgNP content for the same temperatures. In comparison, we found our maximum conductivity value at 7.7 vol.% AgNP to be slightly lower than those reported by Chen et al. but the PT agrees with their data [38]. This difference can be attributed to different factors such as the composite preparation method, particle sizes, and the synthesized AgNP method.

The percolation threshold for conductivity in conductive composites can be reached in two main ways: by adding conductive filler to an insulating polymer without changing the overall volume or compressing a composite that initially contains too little filler to conduct electricity [39]. As shown in Figure 9, increasing the pressure at the same filler concentration leads to higher conductivity. When the concentration of AgNPs increases, the pressure required to trigger a sharp rise in conductivity decreases—this point is referred to as the pressure threshold. The pressure effect on the composite is likely related to a reduction in film thickness, which brings AgNPs closer together and helps form a conductive network. According to percolation theory, once this network forms at the pressure threshold, the material's conductivity can increase by several orders of magnitude. The specific pressure at which this dramatic change occurs depends

FIGURE 6 | Optical microscopy images in-plane for PU-AgNPs nanocomposite (a) without the washing step with DMF and (b–g) with the washing step with DMF showing different content of AgNPs dispersed in PU for concentration of AgNPs: (b) 43.3 wt.%; (c) 25.2 wt.%; (d) 20.6 wt.%; (e) 12.8 wt.%; (f) 9.6 wt.%; (g) 6.8 wt.%.

FIGURE 7 | SEM image of the AgNPs-PU composite (a, c) without the washing step with DMF and (b–d) with the washing step with DMF showing a content of about 20 wt.% AgNPs dispersed. (a, b) SEM images in the plane and (c, d) images through the thickness.

FIGURE 8 | (a) Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA) and (b) the first derivative of TGA curves for AgNPs-PU composite films with a concentration of AgNPs: 6.8 wt. % (red), 20.5 wt.% (black), 36.2 wt.% (green) and 43.3 wt.% (blue).

FIGURE 9 | Experimental electrical conductivity versus vertical pressures for green AgNP-PU four concentrations of AgNPs: (blue) 43.3 wt.% (orange) 36.2 wt.% (gray) 20.5 wt.% (green) 6.8 wt.%.

on several factors, including filler orientation, polymer deformation, filler shape, and the geometry of the composite itself. The literature has widely reported similar pressure-dependent electrical behavior in conductive composites [40–42]. The sharp rise in conductivity at the pressure threshold makes AgNPs-PU composites particularly promising for pressure sensing and switching applications.

In the initial phase, the reliability of the simulation was assessed by comparing experimental and simulation results for a composite containing 43.3 wt.% AgNPs in PU under different pressures. Figure 10 illustrates this comparison, and Figure 11 represents examples of generated geometries for AgNPs in PU with the

existence of stabilizers. Although discrepancies were observed between experimental and simulation results at applied pressures below 2 kPa, both followed a similar trend. This deviation may be attributed to the multimeter's inability to accurately measure the resistance of materials for such low conductivity levels (i.e., detection limit). In the simulation results, when the applied pressure was increased to 2 kPa, no significant jump in conductivity was observed. However, a substantial increase in conductivity by several orders of magnitude was noted when the pressure was increased from 2 to 10 kPa in both experimental and simulation results. At 20 kPa, the conductivity continued to increase gradually. However, the increment was negligible compared to the previous pressure step. The maximum conductivity in both the experiment and simulation was observed at the highest applied pressure of 20 kPa, demonstrating a strong correlation between experimental and simulation results. The slight discrepancies between the experimental and simulation results could be attributed to the lower concentration of stabilizer used in the simulations. Therefore, it was decided to investigate the effect of the stabilizer on the conductivity.

The impact of stabilizer concentration on the electrical conductivity of AgNPs-PU was assessed through FE-RVE simulation. In the simulation, we adjusted using the volume percent of the stabilizer rather than its mass, as the change in the stabilizer's mass would not affect the mass fraction due to silver's density being 10 times greater than that of the stabilizer. The simulations were conducted to examine how variations in the stabilizer's volume percent impacted the composite's conductivity at different AgNP concentrations, ranging from 10 to 30 wt.% (1.3 to 4.67 vol.%). The optical microscope image analysis of AgNPs-PU (see Figures 4a and 6a) revealed that the initial stabilizer concentration in green AgNPs, with no removal steps, was approximately 30 vol.%. TGA of the green AgNPs Figure 3 also corroborated this. It was then assumed that 10 vol.% of the stabilizer was removed during each washing step. Consequently, the stabilizer concentration was simulated to decrease from 30% to 10% vol in 10% vol increments. This corresponds from 19.8 to 8.2 in 8.2 wt.%. Figure S4 illustrates the generated geometries for simulated composites based on the employed assumptions.

Figure 12 shows how the simulated conductivity of the AgNPs-PU composite varies with different stabilizer volume percent for three filler concentrations, including AgNPs and

FIGURE 10 | Comparison between the experimental and simulated electrical conductivity of AgNPs-PU obtained with 43.3 wt.% of AgNPs: (i) Experiments and (ii) Simulations.

FIGURE 11 | The 3D RVEs simulated geometries represent the composite film with 43.3 wt.% of AgNPs and 4 wt.% of stabilizers under different pressures: (a) 0 kPa, (b) 5 kPa, (c) 10 kPa, and (d) 20 kPa. In blue are the AgNPs, and in red are the stabilizers.

FIGURE 12 | Simulated electrical conductivity using FE-RVE of AgNPs-PU composite versus the stabilizer concentration for different amounts AgNPs: The gray curve points represent 30 wt.% (4.67 vol.%) AgNPs; The orange curve points represent 20 wt.% (2.78 vol.%) AgNPs; the blue curve-points represent 10 wt.% (1.26 vol.%) AgNPs; and the empty Symbols represent experimental results: The black is 43.3 wt.% AgNPs; purple is 36.2 wt.% AgNPs; green is 20.5 wt.% AgNPs.

stabilizers, from the simulation studies in the Z direction without the effect of pressure. At the highest AgNP concentration of 30 wt.% (as shown by the gray line in Figure 12), the electrical conductivity of AgNPs-PU remains constant, indicating that it is unaffected by the stabilizer concentration. AgNPs form clusters that consistently create electron pathways, ensuring the composite remains conductive regardless of other factors. The effect of stabilizers became noticeable when the concentration of AgNPs was reduced. At 20 wt.% silver nanoparticles, the composite became nearly insulating with 30 vol.% stabilizers, showing a conductivity of 5.6×10^{-5} S/m. Reducing the stabilizers to 20 vol.% raised the conductivity to 1.3×10^{-4} S/m, but still, the composite is almost in a non-conductive state. A further reduction in stabilizers to 10 vol.% turned the composite conductive, with a conductivity of 5.17 S/m. Similar behavior was found when the concentration of AgNPs was about 10 wt.%. In this scenario, the conductivity values for composites were 0.193 and 2.46×10^{-6} S/m for 10 and 30 vol.% of stabilizers, respectively. The only difference is the lower conductivity values in the composite with 10 wt.% AgNPs than the composite with 20 wt.%

AgNPs. In Figure 12, we have added the experimental conductivity data for the nanocomposite produced in this work. It can be seen from the figure that experimental data are in agreement with the simulation for 20 wt.% AgNPs and 10 wt.% AgNPs for that specific range of concentration stabilizer. The lower experimental conductivity compared to the simulation results could be due to certain assumptions made in the simulations, such as modeling the stabilizer as spherical particles and not capturing the possibility of the oxidation of the AgNPs.

4 | Conclusions

In this work, green AgNPs have been synthesized using the *Urtica dioica* (UR). The green AgNPs are relatively small, with a broad size distribution ranging from 10 to 30 nm and an average size of 17 nm. A stabilizing agent was covering the AgNPs, preventing the nanoparticles from agglomerating. The amount of stabilizer was about 38% of the mass of AgNPs. The synthesized AgNPs were incorporated into PU to obtain ECPCs, and it was found that AgNPs-PU composites were non-conductive due to stabilizers encapsulating the AgNPs, preventing electron conduction. A certain number of stabilizers were removed by washing the AgNPs with DMF, and then the AgNPs were added to PU. Composites prepared after removing some stabilizers showed a more uniform dispersion of AgNPs and improved conductivity. The conductivity of AgNP-PU composites increases with both pressure and AgNP concentration, following an S-shaped pattern. The maximum conductivity was 1.4 S/m for the highest concentration of AgNPs (43.3 wt.%) at 20 kPa.

FE-RVE simulations predicted the electrical behavior of the composite under different applied pressures. Although there were minor discrepancies at lower pressures, both experimental and simulation results followed a similar trend. Furthermore, the impact of stabilizer concentration on the electrical conductivity of AgNPs-PU was investigated by FE-RVE simulation for the concentration of silver from 10 to 30 wt.%. At the highest AgNP concentration, the electrical conductivity of AgNPs-PU remains stable, unaffected by stabilizer concentration. The impact of stabilizers only affects the conductivity at lower AgNP concentrations. Simulations supported the idea that the removal of stabilizers is critical for achieving high-conductivity ECPCs. The study highlights

that green AgNPs can be used to obtain ECPCs with improved conductivity, thus advancing more sustainable and efficient electronic applications.

Author Contributions

G.S.M., Y.S.-V., and K.L.: conceptualization. S.M., G.K., and J.K.: methodology. S.M.: simulations. S.M., G.S.M., G.K., Y.S.-V., and S.G.: formal analysis. S.M., G.S.M., G.K., Y.S.-V., and K.L.: investigation. S.M., G.S.M., G.K., and Y.S.-V.: resources. S.M. and Y.S.-V.: writing—original draft preparation. Y.S.-V., G.S.M., G.K., and K.L.: writing—review and editing. Y.S.-V., G.S.M., G.K., S.G., and K.L.: supervision. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that supports the findings of this study are available in the supplementary material of this article.

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Supporting Information

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